

A Projection Surface Has No Face

*A reply, in the spirit of the philosophy of education, to Nima Mina's report on
Reza Pahlavi's European tour*

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Nima Mina's report on Reza Pahlavi's European tour in the spring of 2026 is among the most careful contributions the Iran debate has produced in these months.¹ It is well-informed and, in several places, more generous than the climate allows: it shields the prince from the cheap insinuation of a SAVAK past, it shows how radical fringes are generalised in order to discredit the whole, and it names the silence of the left before the dead of 8 and 9 January. A report of this kind deserves to be thought further – beyond what it itself says.

The report arranges the journey – Italy, Sweden, Germany – into three fields of tension: the ambivalence of European Iran policy, the fragmentation of the opposition in exile, the polarisation of Western debate. It closes on a word that carries the whole analysis: Pahlavi has become, it says, a “projection surface” for competing narratives. It is worth dwelling on that word a little longer.

A Word and Its Cost

Is Reza Pahlavi a surface? He is a man who himself speaks, demands, errs – and who himself projects. To declare him a mere surface is a bold move. For a surface has no face. It receives whatever others cast upon it; it does not speak; it raises no claim. And so one may ask whether the vocabulary with which politics is described – “narrative”, “polarisation”, “discourse” – does not of itself tend to register everything except the one thing on which education lives: the encounter in which a human being addresses us and places us under a claim. Even those who see through the projecting may remain caught in its language – in words that force thought into their own channels, as plastic words do.²

Emmanuel Lévinas let ethics begin where a face looks at us and forbids us to reduce it to our images of it. From here what is at stake becomes visible: a language that turns a human being into a surface keeps the projections and lets the face slip away. What presents itself as sober distance can imperceptibly become appropriation –

¹Nima Mina, *Prince Reza Pahlavi's European Tour in the Spring of 2026: Media Controversies, Diaspora Conflicts, and Europe's Iran Policy*, Hoover Institution (The Caravan Notebook), 5 June 2026.

²Cf. *Das Wort, das blind macht. Wann wird Religion politisch? Eine bildungsphilosophische Besinnung* (The Word That Blinds. When Does Religion Become Political?), Zenodo 2026, DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20491423> – on the “plastic word” that forces thought into its channels.

the other then counts only insofar as he bears narratives foreign to him. What remains to be asked is whether the form itself invites this, quite apart from Mina's intention.

But is it enough to name the projecting? Whoever observes that all camps project remains himself outside the matter, in a safe place above the quarrel. Understanding, though, asks more than registering: it asks that one take a stand – for the truth, not for a person and not for a party. And its beneficiaries, in the end, are always those who suffer.

Objectivity and Fellow-Humanity

Objectivity and fellow-humanity – *Sachlichkeit* and *Mitmenschlichkeit* – are two words that must not fall apart. Fidelity to the matter and responsibility for one's fellow human being belong together; the one is fulfilled in the other. Mina's report attains a high objectivity. The question is whether, in places, it does not loosen itself from the fellow-humanity it ought to serve. A sign of this lies in the form. To every suffering a counter-claim is set beside it, to every massacre a second reading; the dead of January appear as stations in a study of polarisation. This symmetry can create the impression of an equivalence that the matter does not possess – as though the sentence “the regime shot the defenceless” stood on the same level as the sentence “Pahlavi stands too close to Israel”.

The killing on the eighth and ninth of January either happened or did not; it is no narrative, and here the true admits no degree – something is true, or it is not. Whoever dissolves what happened into competing narratives makes, without willing it, a decision and calls it neutrality. And so a silence arises in which victim and perpetrator stand before the same measure. Perhaps it is precisely the balanced account, which holds itself to be the most considerate, that does the one who was shot the least justice: it leaves open whether any wrong was done to him at all.

The Question of the Mandate

The report returns more than once to a true sentence: under the regime there are no reliable surveys, no “verified mandate”. The sentence holds. Yet what does it effect within the structure of the analysis? Does it not demand a measure that, under dictatorship, no one can meet – and thereby defer judgement indefinitely? Education shows itself precisely in the capacity to answer responsibly without the comfort of certainty. The one who was shot does not wait for the survey.

It is striking, moreover, that this measure is applied to one side only. From the figure of the opposition a “verified mandate” is expected; the regime, which prevents every verification by force, is spared the same question. And so the impossibility the regime produces turns, quietly, into an argument against its

opponents. One may ask whether a scepticism that holds itself especially wakeful does not here assist the very thing it means to see through.

Where Does the Rift Run?

Whoever looks for the human being behind the narratives is led into politics. And now to what the report leaves open: the question of where the decisive rift runs. Mina places it in the diaspora and in the chancelleries of Europe – fragmentation here, ambivalence there. Yet does the rift that matters not run within Iran: between the few who live off the apparatus and the many who suffer under it? Whoever sees this understands too why, among many opponents of the regime in Iran, hope turns precisely to the United States and Israel – to those powers credited above all with the capacity to oppose the regime effectively. No road leads east: Russia and China have long stood at the regime’s side; Germany and France have, through their policy of appeasement toward the regime, forfeited much trust. What remains, for whoever is offered a hand at all, are above all Washington and Jerusalem as effective external points of reference – in the clear knowledge that these powers act from interest, not from love of humanity, and that their governments are contested at home. This turning is the choice of one who has no other; it has nothing to do with naivety. How great it is cannot be captured in numbers under dictatorship; yet it is loud enough to be perceived by anyone willing to hear and to see.

Whoever makes the fragmentation of exile and the caution of Europe the subject may shift the gaze away from this rift – toward the standpoint of the outside observer, for whom Iran is a problem of foreign policy rather than a place where human beings are laid claim to by an unbearable present. And it remains to be asked where the wedge comes from that is driven into the inner rift: does it not come in part from exile itself, from an intelligentsia that takes itself for the conscience of the movement and yet shares in its division?

Here the report supplies the material itself. It records that left-wing and anti-imperialist opponents of Pahlavi in Italy, Sweden and Germany largely kept silent before the massacres of 8 and 9 January, and in part took over the narrative of an Israeli-American conspiracy. It is worth dwelling a moment on this finding. How is one to understand that, before the dead, words are found for the distant conspiracy and not one for those near at hand? A stance that always seeks the chief culprit in the West must, presumably, diminish the nearer one. The report relates that monarchists raise this objection; it does not make the objection its own. Does it strike any less for that?

The same displacement touches Pahlavi’s distinction – Iran, the nation, is not the “Islamic Republic”, the regime – which the report classes as “politically insufficient” because violence has civilian consequences. This distinction is an act of thought. Whoever lets “Iran” and the “Islamic Republic” collapse into one takes over the

regime's deepest claim: that it is itself Iran. And whoever no longer distinguishes the people from the power that oppresses them loses the people from view. So the balanced account repeats, without willing it, what the regime asserts of itself.

The Pattern of 1979

Whence this attention to the inner rift? From an experience Iran has had. In 1979 a broad movement – students, bazaaris, intellectuals, religious milieus – carried the fall of the Shah. It was captured by a small, highly organised minority: Khomeini's clerical movement. Many wanted freedom, justice, national self-determination; Khomeini knew what he wanted. What remained was the “Islamic Republic” – a name that forces together two words which exclude each other, at least where republic means the self-legislation of free citizens and not merely a method of voting.³

The question of that time returns today: is there an organised democratic force to fill an emerging vacuum before others do? The networks of the Revolutionary Guards, the Basij, the religious foundations do not vanish with the regime; they transform themselves – into economic actors, local structures of power, new movements. The danger of a transition therefore lies less in foreign interference than in the inner consolidation of those already organised, while the democrats are still seeking their form.

Among these organised forces are also nostalgic restorers, who readily blur the difference between transition and restoration, and demonstrators who carry SAVAK symbols as though repression were forgivable once it served one's own side. That too belongs to the picture. A future Iran would have to be guarded against the temptation of restoration as much as against the return of the clergy – and against any oligarchy or community of interest that would set itself in its place.

Federalism and Secession: A Difference That Counts

One objection of the report carries justly: monarchist discourse, it says, often overhears the question of minorities, and Kurdish voices criticise its centralism. The objection touches something true – and yet does not lead of itself where it is turned. For it blurs a difference on which much hangs: that between secessionists and federalists. Kurds, Azerbaijanis, Baloch, Arab Iranians in Khuzestan pursue differing aims. Few demand secession; most demand autonomy, cultural rights, participation, decentralisation. That is federalism – and federalism can secure territorial unity rather than harm it. Switzerland shows it daily. Perhaps a future Iran that does not institutionally recognise the diversity of its ethnic and regional communities builds on sand, and drives those who fight for freedom today into the

³Ibid. – on the “Islamic Republic” as a *contradictio in adiecto*.

fight for secession tomorrow, because no other road remains. The justified objection then calls for more federalism – as a demand on every transitional figure, the monarchic as much as the republican. A community that counts only as part of a whole and not as itself is described and administered before it is heard – that too is a way of letting a face become a surface.

The Charge of Emptiness

From here the gravest charge can be examined, which the report – with the taz – lets stand: that Pahlavi formulates appeals but no concepts; that conceptions are lacking of transitional structures, minority rights, democratic legitimacy. But is that so? Since July 2025 there has existed, in the “Emergency Phase Booklet” of the Iran Prosperity Project, prepared for the National Union for Democracy in Iran (NUFDI), a worked-out plan. It describes the first hundred to hundred-and-eighty days after the fall of the regime, divides into fourteen white papers, sketches a three-part transitional system, anchors seven inviolable founding principles – among them the full separation of religion and state – and traces a roadmap, by way of two referendums, to a new constitution. Whoever knows this document will hardly maintain the charge of emptiness.

This does not place the document beyond all doubt; on the contrary. It bears grave structural defects, and to name them belongs to the same objectivity. It claims democratic legitimacy and yet rests on an authority not previously legitimated: the “Leader of the National Uprising” appoints the heads of government and of justice, as well as the members of the transitional legislature, whose mere consultation binds him to nothing in law; and so a feedback loop arises in which all powers run back to one person. The rule of law thus rests on a pledge – Pahlavi has assured the protection of dissidents more than once, by word – where it would have to rest on an instance that measures his decrees against the founding principles. The real factors of power no decree dissolves: the Revolutionary Guards, the Basij, and above all the bonyads, which control a great part of the economy, are deeply intergrown social structures. And about the fourth pillar – parties, a free press, trade unions, civil society – the document is silent; in 1979 the street fell first, then the constitution. Seen thus, the critics’ deeper worry holds: it is less about the existence of the concepts than about whether they will bear weight. And whether they bear weight is decided by whether an order still sees the individual for whom it is made, or only administers its own offices.

And yet such a document deserves, in the end, assent – a calculated assent, bound to conditions. The reason is sober: Pahlavi is at present the only figure with a power of convergence both national and international; the ideal one he is not. Political action takes place under the conditions of the possible. An assent of this kind names, in the same breath, the criteria under which it would have to be revoked;

whoever names no criteria of revocation props up, in the end, a person and not a transition.

An examination of this kind – thorough, demanding, and in the end assenting – was submitted to NUFDI in March 2026.⁴ No answer followed. And so a deafness on both sides shows itself: the criticism overlooks the substance, the movement fails to hear the counsel. Both are the same – the failure to answer the one who comes forward.

What Would Remain

What, then, would remain to be wished for Mina's report? That it recall what objectivity is for: for the laying open of a space in which the matter, and the human being who suffers it, can make their claim heard – more than for the cool registering of narratives. The objectivity itself it should keep; fidelity to the matter is the beginning of all education, and the report keeps it over long stretches. What would matter is that this objectivity not loosen itself from the fellow-humanity in whose service it stands, and that over the registering of camps the human being who suffers the situation not disappear.

To follow the truth spares no side. For just this reason there may be demanded of Pahlavi what scarcely anyone demands of him – a constitutional control that binds him himself; and for just this reason the regime loses, with the name "Iran", the very thing to which it clings most strongly.

What Mina has laid before us is a careful report on the narratives that others form about Pahlavi. What it leaves open are the facts against which those narratives are to be measured: the dead of January, the transitional document now in hand, the rift within Iran. Whoever takes up these facts moves beyond the registering of narratives – to where the real engagement begins.

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Zürich, June 2026

The German version of this essay is available on Zenodo:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20591663>

⁴*Übergang ohne Garantie? Reza Pahlavis Emergency Phase Plan (Transition without Guarantee?)*, Zenodo, 7 March 2026, DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18904500>.